

Milestone: MS31 - Federated learning technologies

Lead Participant: BSC and DKFZ

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Due: June 2024

Date Of Completion: 22/05/2024

Means of Verification

Deliverable 8.5 (<https://zenodo.org/records/11550561>)
GDI WP7/WP8 Flattening Federated Processing Technologies to Prototypical Questions

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

BSC (Spain), DKFZ (Germany), P4DAB (Portugal), VIB (Belgium)

Next action steps

Define primary and secondary workflow engine choices

Discuss loosely-coupled integration around GA4GH standards for workflow and task execution (WES/TES), data access (AAI/REMS) and encryption (Crypt4GH)

Integrate federated learning frameworks like Flower into the technical solution

Offer training modules on workflow engines and federated learning

